

**SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF IMPROVING
PSYCHOLOGICAL CULTURE IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES**

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Annotation: The formation of psychological culture in future pedagogues is one of the most important tasks of today. The article presents the ideas of improving the pedagogical mechanisms of preparing the future and the socio-psychological mechanisms of improving the psychological culture of future pedagogues in the socio-pedagogical activity of teachers of higher educational institutions. , about the work of teachers and members of the scientific community.

Key words: education, pedagogue-psychologist, student, socio-pedagogical activity, training, psychological awareness, specialist

Аннотация: Формирование психологической культуры у будущих педагогов является одной из важнейших задач современности. В статье представлены идеи совершенствования педагогических механизмов подготовки будущего и социально-психологических механизмов повышения психологической культуры будущих педагогов в социально-педагогической деятельности преподавателей высших учебных заведений. , о работе преподавателей и членов научного сообщества.

Ключевые слова: образование, педагог-психолог, студент, социально-педагогическая деятельность, подготовка, психологическое сознание, специалист.

In order to develop the professional mobility of the future specialist, in order to adequately fulfill his duties, it is necessary to transfer the socio-cultural space of the university to the real educational space, because the identification of the elements of the socio-cultural space and their positive content in the educational process is determined by the individual. There are not enough signs indicating that it is being used. It should be noted that higher educational institutions are an important educational link in our country, developing the spirituality of young people and preparing future teachers for social and pedagogical activities. In the current era, it is important to connect young people with the life and goals of the changing world societies, to help young people find their place in society. Education system political, economic, The need to connect with socio-pedagogical and spiritual spheres is becoming a task of changes in society. A person constantly

changes his place in the socio-cultural space, moves from one place to another, from one subject to another. and thereby narrates the biography of his events. Mobility in space, immutability of different views creates special conditions for initiative and independence, creativity and self-affirmation, freedom of social and creative direction, evaluation and preferences, which ultimately lead to the development of a future specialist. helps to develop professional mobility. Today, special attention is paid to the training of personnel who meet the requirements of the 21st century. The development of social activity of students becomes an important factor in the period of intensive high technical development of the society. At the same time, the creation of pedagogical mechanisms for the development of social activity in students of pedagogy and the psychology of higher educational institutions. Accordingly, the importance of ensuring the development of social activity of students of pedagogy and psychology of higher educational institutions is rapidly increasing. The content of the concept of development of social activity among students is enriched with innovative concepts, and it is necessary to integrate this updated content into all stages of the educational system and introduce it into the educational process. An important task is to shed light on the problem of pedagogical mechanisms for the development of social activity in students of pedagogy and psychology of higher educational institutions and to analyze them as an object of scientific research. Thus, the main mechanism of personality development is the mechanism of cultural and personal identification, the functioning of which is ensured by a certain level of development of mechanisms, and pedagogical mechanisms are based on the creation of conditions for the formation and development of professional mobility. its most general form, cultural and personal identification should be understood as the subject's identification with another subject. Therefore, the mechanism of cultural and personal identification promotes the formation of intellectual and moral experience of a person. considered as a resonant response to the riding environment. funds. In this case, his main task is not to solve the problem itself, but to acquire the necessary knowledge, skills, and methods of action. can become education, but not for others, therefore, the organization of students' life activities should be based on the ideas of a person-oriented approach. It represents a part of the educational field of this person. Since the importance of different events for each person is different, we should talk about the individual learning space of a person. Involvement of the student in the happenings is the main condition for pedagogical influence on the educational field. The environment of socio-cultural education should become an

educational environment. Accordingly, It is necessary to implement specific psychological and pedagogical mechanisms to ensure the transfer of the socio-cultural environment to the educational environment, and a specific event to the event. The main thing is to understand the mechanisms of personality development of the future specialist. The event is characterized by the external participation of the student in a situation characterized by a clear distribution of roles, a description of the requirements for the performance of this role. It should be taken into account that any event is characterized by emotional and valuable involvement in the situation based on participatory communication. Attention is paid to the improvement of the methodological-legal, material-technical base of higher education institutions, and the continuation of this process plays an important role in the preparation of educational institutions and students for socio-pedagogical activities.

- 1) education manifested in the continuous development of the doctrine of national goals and objectives;
- 2) the idea of creating mechanisms for the development of social activity of students, the content of reform and improvement of education in higher education institutions and its practical aspects.

Improving the management of activities of higher educational institutions requires carrying out educational work, that is, in accordance with the requirements of higher education. As a result, the implementation of monitoring in educational institutions has become an important source and means of independent education activities related to the training of future pedagogical psychologists as social and pedagogical personnel. Conducting pedagogical activity of students at a social and educational institution at a high scientific-pedagogical level; improves their knowledge about social activity, educational work. As a result, it is an important mechanism and, among other things, in preparing students for socio-pedagogical activities. Education has its own organizational features. Responsible leaders, scientists, organizers of the educational process, the process of leading the organization of preparing students for socio-pedagogical activities, raising the issue of effective use of modern textbooks, scientific, theoretical, methodological and general pedagogical literature. As part of measures to improve the training of future teachers and psychologists in education, changes will be made to the curriculum. Also, such a solution to the problem, that is, the activity of developing the content of the preparation of future teachers for socio-pedagogical education, occupies an important place. It should be noted that the educational process is designed in

accordance with the educational requirements of the near future. General and special purpose higher education for training future pedagogues-psychologists teaching subjects, which consists of determining the set of lim, improving them based on the requirements of the time, the content of each subject is included in the curriculum, the total amount of educational materials, taking into account the total, providing students with work. includes.

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